

SOME ASPECTS OF ALLERGIC RHINITIS (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Abstract. *The article describes the etiology, clinical picture, differential diagnosis and the significant role of doctors in improving the quality of medical care for patients with this disease is noted. Allergic rhinitis is an atopic disease characterized by sneezing, nasal congestion, watery discharge, and nasal itching. It is caused by an IgE-mediated immune response to inhaled allergens: an immediate-phase reaction develops first, followed by a late-phase reaction associated with the action of leukotrienes.*

Keywords: *allergic rhinitis, etiology, epidemiology, differential diagnosis and treatment of allergic rhinitis.*

Introduction. It is widely acknowledged that allergic rhinitis (AR) is a common condition affecting patients of all ages. It contributes to the development of significant functional impairment, decreased work capacity, and limitations of daily activities, as well as leads to social problems, negatively impacting sleep, learning, professional activity, general well-being, and quality of life [26]. AR is an atopic disorder and presents with a complex of symptoms including nasal congestion, watery discharge, sneezing, postnasal drip, and nasal itching. The disease affects approximately one in six people and is characterized by high prevalence, leading to decreased work capacity and increased healthcare costs. Previously, AR was considered a pathological process affecting exclusively the nasal airways. However, the concept of "unity of the airways" considers it a component of the body's systemic allergic response associated with concomitant conditions such as bronchial asthma and atopic dermatitis, which share common pathogenetic mechanisms [9-4].

Depending on the course of the disease, AR is divided into seasonal (intermittent) and year-round (persistent): approximately 20% of cases are seasonal, 40% are year-round, and another 40% of patients exhibit a combination of both [23]. In addition to nasal manifestations, patients with AR often experience allergic conjunctivitis, dry cough, Eustachian tube dysfunction, and chronic sinusitis. It has been extensively argued that AR is treatable with various therapeutic methods, with topical glucocorticosteroids considered first-line drugs.[18]

Non-IgE-mediated hyperreactivity can develop as a result of eosinophilic infiltration and structural changes in the nasal mucosa. As a result, the mucosa becomes hypersensitive to nonspecific irritants, such as tobacco smoke and cold air, leading to sneezing, rhinorrhea, and nasal itching [17]. There is evidence suggesting the possible involvement of genetic factors in the development of allergic rhinitis, but high-quality studies in this area are limited. In monozygotic twins, the concordance rate for the development of allergic rhinitis is 45–60%, while in dizygotic twins it is approximately 25%. Furthermore, a link between allergic reactions and certain regions of chromosomes 3 and 4 has been identified [25].

Epidemiological data indicate that the prevalence of allergic rhinitis based on physician diagnosis is approximately 15%, while among patients with nasal symptoms, this figure can reach

30%. It is known that the peak incidence of allergic rhinitis is observed in the second to fourth decades of life, followed by a gradual decline [25]. In the pediatric population, the incidence of allergic rhinitis also remains high, making it one of the most common chronic diseases in children. According to the International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Childhood, symptoms of rhinoconjunctivitis associated with allergic rhinitis are detected in 14.6% of children aged 13-14 years and in 8.5% of children aged 6-7 years [18]. Seasonal allergic rhinitis is more common in children, while persistent allergic rhinitis is more common in adults [2].

According to a 2023 statistical review, 3.6% of adults were forced to miss work, and 36% experienced decreased productivity due to allergic rhinitis. Economic research indicates that the majority of indirect costs are associated with lost productivity due to allergic manifestations [1]. Risk factors for the development of allergic rhinitis include a strong family history of atopy, male gender, the presence of allergen-specific IgE, total serum IgE levels above 100 IU/mL before the age of 6 years, and higher socioeconomic status [25]. Studies conducted among young children have revealed an increased likelihood of developing AR in those who were introduced to complementary foods or formula early and/or were heavily exposed to tobacco smoke during the first year of life [23].

Many studies have examined the possible link between environmental pollution and the development of allergic rhinitis; however, a convincing quantitative correlation has not yet been established. However, factors that potentially have a protective effect on the development of AR have been identified. For example, the role of breastfeeding is actively debated: despite the lack of definitive evidence of its preventive effect on AR, it remains recommended due to its numerous proven benefits and the absence of negative consequences.

There is no reliable evidence that avoiding contact with pets in childhood prevents the development of allergic rhinitis; on the contrary, it is assumed that early contact with animals may contribute to the development of immune tolerance. In recent years, interest in the so-called "farmer effect" in the context of allergic diseases has increased. The results of eight meta-analyses on children in the first year of life living in rural areas demonstrated a reduction in the risk of developing allergic rhinitis by approximately 40% compared to the urban population. [27]

The number of diagnostic approaches exist for assessing allergic rhinitis. A thorough history and physical examination remain the most common and accessible method for establishing a diagnosis. A positive clinical response to a trial of intranasal glucocorticosteroids may provide additional confirmation of the diagnosis. Definitive confirmation of allergic rhinitis is achieved either by measuring allergen-specific IgE in the serum or by skin allergy testing [26]. The American Academy of Otolaryngology guidelines emphasize that allergy testing is appropriate for patients who do not respond to empirical treatment or when identifying a specific allergen is necessary for targeted therapy [18]. Serum testing does not require the participation of specially trained personnel and does not require prior discontinuation of antihistamines, thereby avoiding deterioration in the patient's quality of life.

Skin allergy testing, in contrast, requires a qualified specialist, but its results can be obtained almost immediately. To more accurately identify the causative allergens in patients with seasonal manifestations of the disease, testing is recommended during the period of peak symptom severity [26]. Skin tests are known to have slightly higher sensitivity compared to serum methods and are more cost-effective. However, skin allergy testing has a number of contraindications, including uncontrolled or severe bronchial asthma, unstable cardiovascular disease, pregnancy, and the concomitant use of β -blockers. Furthermore, H₂-receptor antagonists, tricyclic

antidepressants, and the anti-IgE monoclonal antibody omalizumab can interfere with skin test results, and therefore it is recommended to temporarily discontinue them before testing.[27].

It should be noted that radiographic examination is generally not used to diagnose allergic rhinitis and is used primarily to exclude other conditions, particularly rhinosinusitis [23,27]. Treatment is based on minimizing exposure to triggers, especially in patients with seasonal symptoms, although complete avoidance of allergens is not always possible. Preventive measures aimed at reducing exposure to household allergens, such as dust mites, animal hair and dander, and upholstered furniture, are possible; however, such interventions often require significant lifestyle changes and may be unacceptable to the patient. If removing the pet from the home is not possible, limiting its presence to one room to reduce exposure to allergens is considered an acceptable option. It should be noted that complete elimination of cat dander from a living space may take up to 20 weeks, even after removing the pet. Using hypoallergenic bedding, washing linens in hot water, and using vacuum cleaners with high-efficiency particulate air (HEPA) filters can significantly reduce the severity of symptoms [25].

Drug treatment for allergic rhinitis includes antihistamines, intranasal glucocorticosteroids, leukotriene receptor antagonists, and allergen-specific immunotherapy. Intranasal corticosteroids can be used either as monotherapy or in combination with oral antihistamines in patients with mild, moderate, and severe manifestations of the disease. Studies have demonstrated that intranasal corticosteroids are superior to antihistamines in their ability to reduce inflammation of the nasal mucosa and improve its condition.

Therefore, topical intranasal steroids are considered first-line therapy for allergic rhinitis [28]. The most common nasal sprays include beclomethasone, budesonide, fluticasone propionate, mometasone furoate, and triamcinolone acetonide. Proper technique for using nasal sprays is crucial for achieving maximum therapeutic effect and reducing the risk of adverse reactions, so patients should receive detailed instructions on their use. These medications should be used regularly, as the maximum effect develops within a few days. It is recommended to insert the spray into the nostril and point it laterally, toward the corresponding eye, to minimize contact of the spray with the nasal septum. The most common adverse events are nasal irritation and nosebleeds, which can be prevented with proper spray technique [24].

Although oral and injectable glucocorticosteroids can reduce the symptoms of allergic rhinitis, they are not recommended for routine use due to the significant risk of systemic side effects. [27]. First-generation antihistamines include diphenhydramine, chlorpheniramine, and hydroxyzine, while fexofenadine, loratadine, desloratadine, and cetirizine represent the second generation of these agents. Both groups of medications effectively reduce the symptoms of allergic rhinitis. However, first-generation antihistamines have a pronounced sedative effect due to their ability to penetrate the blood-brain barrier. They also interact with muscarinic receptors, which can lead to side effects such as dry mouth, urinary retention, constipation, and tachycardia.

Second-generation antihistamines are characterized by greater selectivity for H1 receptors, less sedative effects, and a longer half-life of 12 to 24 hours compared to first-generation medications. Fexofenadine causes virtually no drowsiness, while loratadine and desloratadine can cause sedation when used in high doses. Cetirizine, in turn, has the greatest sedative potential among second-generation antihistamines. It should be noted that no single drug has a clear advantage over the others, as they all demonstrate comparable efficacy and safety profiles for relieving allergic rhinitis symptoms [25].

Topical antihistamines, such as azelastine, have a rapid onset of action and are superior to oral formulations in reducing nasal symptoms. They are recommended as first- or second-line therapy for allergic rhinitis and can be used in combination with intranasal glucocorticosteroids, providing a synergistic therapeutic effect [27]. Leukotriene receptor antagonists (LTRAs), including montelukast and zafirlukast, can be used to treat allergic rhinitis; however, they are inferior in efficacy to intranasal glucocorticosteroids [20]. These drugs are most often used as part of combination therapy in patients with severe disease or in those with an inadequate response to standard therapy.

In cases where allergen avoidance measures and combination drug therapy do not produce a satisfactory clinical effect, it is advisable to consider allergen-specific immunotherapy. The most common methods are subcutaneous (ASIT) and sublingual (SLIT) immunotherapy. Treatment typically begins with weekly administration of gradually increasing doses for 6–8 months, followed by a maintenance regimen lasting 3–5 years. Patients typically experience a long-lasting protective effect, allowing for subsequent discontinuation of therapy [18]. It is well known that oral decongestants, such as pseudoephedrine, can reduce the severity of symptoms; however, their continuous daily use is not recommended due to potential side effects. Intranasal vasoconstrictors, such as xylometazoline, are alpha-adrenergic agonists and act directly on the nasal mucosa, causing vasoconstriction.

Long-term use of nasal decongestants carries a high risk of developing rebound nasal congestion, known as rhinitis medicamentosa, and therefore their use should not exceed one week [27]. Sodium cromoglycate (cromolyn) effectively reduces symptoms such as sneezing, runny nose, and itching, making it a reasonable treatment option. Surgical treatment is indicated for patients with nasal polyposis, inferior turbinate hypertrophy causing intractable nasal congestion, or chronic paranasal sinus disease refractory to medical treatment [12,25,29]. Budesonide is the only glucocorticosteroid approved for use in pregnant women with symptoms of allergic rhinitis [18]. The monoclonal antibody omalizumab may be an effective treatment option for patients with AR; however, its high cost limits its widespread use [3]. Nasal saline solutions may also be used in combination with other treatments: isotonic solutions are more commonly used in adults, while hypertonic solutions may be more effective in children [27].

Differential diagnosis of allergic rhinitis includes exclusion of other types of rhinitis not associated with allergies. These include vasomotor rhinitis, infectious rhinitis, pregnancy rhinitis, hormonally induced rhinitis, nonallergic rhinitis with eosinophilia (NARES), chemical rhinitis, drug-induced rhinitis, as well as autoimmune, granulomatous, and vasculitic rhinitis, nasal polyposis, nasopharyngeal neoplasms, cerebrospinal fluid leakage, and sickle cell anemia. Children, especially those under 2 years of age, should also be examined for congenital causes of nasal congestion, such as choanal atresia and immunodeficiencies [23, 26, 27].

According to clinical guidelines by E.R. Terenkova and D.V. Terenkov, desloratadine for seasonal allergic rhinitis is recommended to be started 1–2 weeks before the expected pollen season. The drug is also indicated for perennial allergic rhinitis as a baseline therapy for mild cases. For moderate to severe forms of allergic rhinitis, intranasal glucocorticosteroids are prescribed in combination with desloratadine or other second-generation antihistamines. The selection and combination of baseline therapy medications is individualized, taking into account the severity of symptoms, drug tolerability, and the patient's lifestyle. Long-term experience with desloratadine demonstrates its high efficacy in both seasonal and perennial allergic rhinitis. The drug has a high

safety profile and can be combined with other medications, making it an advantage among other antihistamines used to treat allergic rhinitis [26,30].

Chronic rhinosinusitis, although distinct from allergic rhinitis, can develop as a complication of the latter. It is characterized by inflammation of the nasal cavity with symptoms of congestion or discharge persisting for more than three months. Chronic rhinosinusitis often leads to the development of nasal polyps, which arise from long-term inflammation of the paranasal sinus mucosa. Nasal polyps are typically benign and occur symmetrically on both sides; the presence of unilateral polyps requires further investigation to rule out malignancy. The incidence of polyps in the population is approximately 4% and is more common in men. Treatment includes topical steroids and nasal irrigation with saline. Surgical removal is considered only in patients who do not respond to drug therapy.[18,23]

It is also known that sensitization to allergens in allergic rhinitis can alter the immunological parameters of the adenoids, which can lead to adenoid hypertrophy.[22] Eustachian tube dysfunction is commonly seen in patients with allergic rhinitis and manifests as ear congestion, otalgia, and ear fullness. Approximately 10 to 40% of patients with allergic rhinitis also have concomitant asthma, with studies showing that asthma is more common in patients with moderate to severe persistent rhinitis. Data from numerous studies confirm that allergic rhinitis is an independent risk factor for the development of asthma, especially if the disease is diagnosed in infancy. Other possible associated complications include otitis media with effusion, chronic cough, and eosinophilic esophagitis, although the extent of the association of these conditions with allergic rhinitis requires further clarification [27–30].

Conclusion

Exacerbations of rhinitis or asthma, as well as the development of anaphylaxis, can be triggered by allergen-specific desensitization (allergy shots). Therefore, staff in departments providing such therapy must have a high level of training in the diagnosis and treatment of severe allergic reactions, as well as have access to emergency medications, especially epinephrine, and airway management equipment. [6, 8]

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